

Fast dynamic docking guided by adaptive electrostatic bias: the MD-Binding approach

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ABSTRACT

Engineering chemical entities to modify how pharmaceutical targets function, as it is done in drug design, requires a good understanding of molecular recognition and binding. In this context, the limitations of statically describing bimolecular recognition, as done in docking/scoring, call for insightful and efficient dynamical investigations. On the experimental side, the

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3 characterization of dynamical binding processes is still in its infancy. Thus, computer
4 simulations, particularly molecular dynamics (MD), are compelled to play a prominent role,
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6 allowing a deeper comprehension of the binding process and its causes and thus a more informed
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8 compound selection, making more significant the computational contribution to drug discovery¹.
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10 Unfortunately, MD-based approaches cannot yet describe complex events without incurring
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12 prohibitive time and computational costs. Here, we present a new method for fully and
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14 dynamically simulating drug-target-complex formations, tested against a real world and
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16 pharmaceutically relevant benchmark set. The method, based on an adaptive, electrostatics-
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18 inspired bias, envisions a campaign of trivially parallel short MD simulations, and a strategy to
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20 identify a near native binding pose from the sampled configurations. At an affordable
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22 computational cost, this method provided predictions of good accuracy also when the starting
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24 protein conformation was different from that of the crystal complex, a known hurdle for
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26 traditional molecular docking². Moreover, along the observed binding routes, it identified some
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28 key features also found by much more computationally expensive plain-MD simulations.
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30 Overall, this methodology represents a significant progress in the description of binding
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32 phenomena.
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41 1. INTRODUCTION

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43 Understanding the mechanisms underlying molecular recognition and binding is pivotal for
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45 several fields (e.g. chemistry, biophysics, drug discovery)³⁻⁵. The scientific community is
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47 historically used to judge the entire binding process by just looking at the “end of the movie”,
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49 namely the structure of the complex. This is mainly due to the availability of experimental
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51 crystallographic structures, which describe the complex with atomic detail. The computational
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53 counterpart of this is molecular docking, which was conceived many years ago and is now a well
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3 established technology, the reference in the field.⁶ However, affordable computational
4 requirements and practical applicability, rather than inherent predictive power and accuracy,
5 have made molecular docking the choice of election⁷. Since its inception, this approach
6 underwent several significant but still incremental improvements.⁸ We believe that the time is
7 now ripe for a scientific and technological shift in mindset, where the dynamic character of
8 binding is considered and analyzed in addition to the single crystallographic structure⁹. The
9 knowledge of binding paths can point to key molecular events, such as gate openings, encounter
10 complexes, and other intermediates, which can in turn suggest modifications to hit compounds¹⁰.
11 Unfortunately, there are not yet established experimental techniques for dynamically and
12 structurally describing such processes at the atomistic level. In contrast, this is a momentous time
13 for computer-aided predictions of events at the molecular scale. Computational capabilities have
14 grown tremendously in recent years, and there has been continuous development of dedicated
15 techniques in this area¹¹. *In silico* approaches, particularly molecular dynamics (MD), are thus
16 the most promising resource for addressing this need^{12, 13}. Indeed, long *plain* MD simulations
17 have already described the spontaneous binding of small organic molecules to biological targets
18 of pharmacological interest, demonstrating both the adequacy of the present force fields and also
19 the feasibility, at least in some cases, of observing rare events^{10, 14, 15}. However, the sampling
20 provided by this approach rarely meets the requirements for statistical significance, which is
21 desirable for quantitatively estimating thermodynamic observables. Moreover, it requires a huge
22 amount of computational resources, far more than the average time allocated to a real-world drug
23 discovery project.

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26 One solution is to combine MD with so-called *enhanced sampling* approaches, whereby
27 shorter but biased simulations energetically and mechanistically characterize binding events¹⁶⁻²⁰.
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3 Indeed, in recent years, the impact of MD in drug design has increased enormously due to
4 several enhanced sampling techniques exploited to investigate the ligand binding process¹². In
5 this field, the most broadly applied techniques are FEP²¹, umbrella sampling²², steered-MD²³,
6 and, markedly, metadynamics, which has been used several times, in its original or funnel
7 version²⁴, to study protein-ligand binding, including for a variety of targets of pharmacological
8 interest²⁵⁻²⁸. More recently, Moro and coworkers addressed the issue of fast MD-based docking
9 simulations for the human adenosine receptor²⁹. Interestingly, several biased approaches perform
10 free-energy estimations as a function of the progress coordinate along a guess binding path,
11 when available^{30, 31}. Overall, if *enhanced sampling* approaches are to be effective, they usually
12 need a quite detailed a priori knowledge of the most relevant degrees of freedom, or collective
13 variables (CVs), for the process at hand. CVs that prove successful for one system cannot easily
14 be extended to different systems, limiting their applicability. Consequently, the success of these
15 methods can be user- and system-dependent.

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17 Here, we propose a new method, dubbed MD-binding, which systematically exploits MD to
18 predict binding complexes and identify plausible binding paths. The aim of the method is
19 enabling the scientist studying binding to make, at a reasonable computational cost,
20 interpretations and predictions in a more informed way, that includes the observation of the “full
21 movie” of the process together with the intrinsic benefit of fully flexible docking. To do this, it
22 takes inspiration from the well-established notion that *electrostatic interactions* play a
23 fundamental role in molecular recognition and binding, being pivotal at both long and short
24 ranges³². Indeed, in nature, the long-range electrostatic behavior allows the interacting partners
25 to spend sufficient time in relative proximity, so that they assume the most suitable conformation
26 for binding. When approaching the final bound conformation, the short-range components begin

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3 providing high specificity to the forming complex. This power has been exploited by some
4 computational approaches applied to systems where electrostatics is known to play an important
5 role^{33, 34}. With respect to those approaches, the dramatic difference of the presented one lies in
6 the assumption that electrostatics-shaped field lines can effectively guide binding also in
7 processes that are not naturally driven by electrostatics. In line with this assumption, we add a
8 contrived attractive multi-centered external bias that acts between the heavy atoms of the binding
9 partners. In protein-ligand binding cases, the bias acts between a subset of the residues of the
10 binding site and the ligand.
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21 The other key aspect of the method is the *adaptivity* of the bias. In this respect, the intensity of
22 the external force is always kept at a fraction of the intensity of the actual physical force felt by
23 the ligand. Moreover, the biasing force gradually switches off as the process moves forward so
24 that, after the conjectured passing of the transition state has occurred, it slowly recovers the
25 behavior of classical unbiased MD. In summary, the added forces are everywhere tangent to the
26 electrostatic field lines generated by the fictitious charges on ligand and binding site. Their
27 intensity is regulated by the adaptivity rules. The method requires the prior identification of
28 binding site residues. This information is usually available before any structure-based study.
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40 The protocol envisions campaigns of several short (20 ns) simulation runs. Here, we
41 demonstrate its performance on a diverse and challenging set of protein-ligand complexes of
42 pharmacological interest, encompassing enzymes, kinases, and GPCRs. Some of the systems
43 have been chosen due to the availability of long plain MD trajectories describing the binding, to
44 be used as a reference. We also tested our approach against a protein-peptide system. In
45 campaigns of about 20 runs each, the method attained at least once near-native binding poses.
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54 We also compared some mechanistic details of our paths with those obtained by plain MD. This
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3 comparison pointed to some common features, indicating a new and powerful way to exploit
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5 molecular simulations in real-case drug design settings at a reasonable computational cost.
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7 8 2. METHODS

9 The protocol consists of a number of steps:

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11 • Characterization of the binding pocket. This is done via the NanoShaper tool³⁵, which
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13 identifies the atoms facing the lumen of the pocket, we call it the “entrance” of the pocket.
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15 Several entrances can be detected.
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18 • Initial ligand positioning. The ligand is positioned with a random orientation at a
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20 predetermined distance, measured in terms of the thickness of the solvation shell around the
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22 ligand, from the entrance of the binding pocket.
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25 • Identification of attracting atoms: the *attractive* (i.e. the atoms of a subset S of the site and
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27 those of the ligand L) and the *switch-off* (S') residues are chosen, as detailed in subsection 2.3.
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30 • Run of the simulation campaign. A number of independent simulation runs are launched in
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32 parallel. In this work, campaigns of 20 runs per entrance gate, each of them during 20ns,
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34 resulted in at least one near native binding pose.
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37 • Post-processing of the resulting trajectories. The unbiased final parts of the trajectories are
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39 taken and clustered with the k-medoids approach presented in Decherchi et al.³¹, imposing
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41 k=20. If the bias never vanishes during a simulation run, then that run is discarded.
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44 • Ranking of the poses. A Scaled MD approach, as described in subsection 2.5, is used to
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46 identify the best candidate binding pose and, consequently, a physically sound binding path.
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49 **2.1. Characterization of the binding pocket and initial ligand positioning.** NanoShaper is
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51 used to characterize the binding site in terms of volume, surface area and constituting residues.
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53 Large and small probe radii of 3.0 and 1.4 Å, respectively, were used. At the same time,
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NanoShaper samples the part of the pocket surface that is accessible from the solvent and defines a set of points that lie at the entrance of the pocket. These dots, and the corresponding outward normal vectors, are clustered in N “gate” sets. The centroid of each cluster (i.e. the representative of the corresponding gate) identifies a possible access of the ligand to the pocket. Consistently, the ligand is positioned away from each gate along the normal, with random orientation. Indeed, no information is provided about the “correct” orientation or the final contacts between the receptor and the ligand.

If there is ligand-protein overlap, or if the hydration shell between the ligand and protein is thinner than 10.0 Å, the ligand is translated farther away from the protein.

2.2. The electrostatic-shaped bias. The MD-binding method envisions an additive external force that is summed to the regular potential energy of the system in a molecular dynamics simulation. The bias consists in a moving umbrella (as per classical steered MD) where, however, the force constant $K(t)$ is adaptively modified along time. The functional form of the bias hence is:

$$\frac{1}{2} C * K(t) * (CV(t) - CV_0(t))^2$$

The pair of attracting atom sets (S as site, L as ligand) must thus be defined. The collective variable $CV(t)$, is the electrostatic energy of the biasing system, and can be expressed as the sum of terms having the following form:

$$CV(t) = \sum_{i \in L, s \in S}^n \frac{Q_i Q_s}{r_{i,s}(t)} \exp(-r_{i,s}(t)/\lambda)$$

where, r are the interatomic distances, $\exp(-r/\lambda)$ is a decay function aimed at avoiding unnecessary long ranged forces, and λ is the parameter that rules the spatial range of the decay (heuristically set to 10 Å).

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3 Fictitious charges are therefore positioned on every attracting atom. In the present
4 implementation: $Q_l = -Q_s \forall l \in L, s \in S$. The absolute value of the charges is not relevant since the
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6 overall intensity is ruled by the C parameter.
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10 The total force field lines result from the vectorial composition of regular and biasing forces.
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12 “By design”, the total force field lines identify a path leading to the binding site, which the
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14 ligand is invited to follow. This path automatically and dynamically updates as the binding site
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16 changes shape along its natural conformational evolution. Importantly, spreading the attraction
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18 across all the atoms of the S and L sets increases the likelihood of synergistic motions and
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20 reduces the likelihood of conformations that are incompatible with the binding due to steric
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22 hindrance.
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26 **2.3. Choice of the attracting and switch-off atoms.** The set L contains all of the ligand’s
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28 heavy atoms. The set S is chosen as a subset of the overall list of atoms constituting the binding
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30 site, which is created with NanoShaper. The choice of the subset is based mostly on geometric
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32 factors. Namely, the heavy atoms of the innermost part of the site are made to be attracting (for
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34 the presently studied systems, see Table S1). The choice of the attracting residues is an important
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36 aspect of the method, and affects its performance. Results of three cases of MD-Binding
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38 approach where the residues at the bottom of the binding pocket have been removed from the S
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40 set are shown in Table S7. The choice of how many atoms should be included in S depends on
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42 several factors, including ligand size, and the size and shape of the binding site. The switch-off
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44 atoms, defined as set S’, should ideally provide an estimate of whether the transition state for the
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46 binding process has been overcome. When the S’ set is approached by the ligand, the intensity of
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48 the biasing force irreversibly and gradually decreases.
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3 **2.4. Dynamics and adaptivity of the bias.** The application of the bias envisages a steering
4 schedule on the collective variable target value $CV_0(t)$, enforcing the reduction of the energy of
5 the contrived electrostatic system. The form of the steer is piecewise linear, and consists of a first
6 part, where the decrease in the target value of the energy is of limited amount to allow
7 reorientation and a minimal conformational rearrangement of the ligand (see Figure S3 in the
8 Supplementary Information). In the following steps of the plan, the decrease becomes more
9 pronounced, increasing the thrust applied to the ligand. The actual target value of the bias,
10 especially in the final part of the steering, is however of limited importance due to the
11 modulation induced by the adaptivity of the protocol, as hereby explained.
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23 The protocol is adaptive in four different respects.

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25 First, the biasing force is always kept below a user-defined threshold. More specifically, the
26 modulus of the biasing force is rescaled at every 0.2 ps of simulation, so that it equals a
27 predefined fraction (10%, of the “real” resulting force acting on the ligand), which originates
28 from the rest of the system. This is done to avoid an overly strong biasing, which could distort
29 the structure of the protein, increasing the probability of following high-energy binding paths.
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37 Second, the bias is further reduced based on the distance between the ligand L and a subset S'
38 of S. S' is a switch-off set comprising atoms that are expected to interact with the ligand (either
39 geometrically or chemically guessed, or a priori known). By monitoring the decrease of the
40 above-mentioned distance, this option seeks to identify the final steps of the process, where the
41 transition state for the binding is already overcome. This makes the bias in this phase particularly
42 unobtrusive, so that the simulation becomes closer to unbiased MD.
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51 The switch-off is obtained via a scaling pre-factor γ , which multiplies the biasing force (this is
52 a component of $K(t)$). This factor is calculated via a switching function as follows:
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$$\gamma = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-ss * (dist - th))}$$

where *ss* and *th* are two suitable parameters, regulating the extent and the steepness of the switching. The value of *dist* equals:

$$dist = \min_{y \in S'} \min_{x \in L} d(x, y),$$

where $d(x,y)$ is the pairwise distance between the *x* and *y* atoms.

A third flavor of adaptivity is introduced into the MD-binding method by adding a “memory effect”. Once the $K(t)$ has begun to decrease due to the approach of the *S'* set, it can no longer increase even if the ligand bounces back. This reduces the likelihood that the ligand reaches the bottom of the pocket, but increases the probability that, if it does, it does this by following physically sound trajectories, which is the highest priority.

Lastly, the dynamical variation of the spring constant is time-averaged over a circular buffer window of 2 ps to ensure that its time variation is consistently smooth.

2.5. Post-processing of the resulting trajectories and ranking of the putative binding conformations. Once the simulation campaign is finished, a pruning process is carried out. This process discards those replicas where either the unbiased MD is not recovered, i.e. the final value of $K(t)$ is greater than 10^{-9} (the ligand did not approach the switch-off set *S'*), or the ligand bounces back from the binding site during the unbiased MD (final distance between ligand and the *S'* set greater than 7 Å). Based on our present experience, roughly half of the simulations can be discarded in this way. Table S2 shows the number of remaining replicas for each case study. The frames present in the unbiased chunks are aligned on the set of attracting residues and then clustered based on the heavy atoms of the ligand using the previously published k-medoids clustering method³¹. Again, based on our experience, 20 clusters characterize the sampled conformations with sufficient detail. The ranking process is based on the evaluation of the

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3 stability of each medoid. Therefore, each medoid conformation is iteratively minimized with the
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5 steepest descent and conjugate gradient methods. Its stability is then estimated along short
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7 unrestrained Scaled Molecular Dynamics (SMD)^{36, 37} runs in the NVT ensemble for 5 ns and
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9 with scaling factor “s” equal to 0.6. In SMD, the potential energy of the entire system is scaled
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11 by a factor s, consequently reducing energetic barriers, including that of ligand unbinding from a
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13 given pose. The rationale underlying this approach is that the best pose should be that exhibiting
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15 the largest stability despite the applied scaling. SMD, used in a more complex protocol, proved
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17 successful in ranking congeneric ligands based on residence time in reasonable amount of
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19 computational time³⁸ and already proved a viable tool to assess pose stability³¹. Table S3 reports
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21 the average RMSD of the SMD simulations and the scoring values from Autodock, Vina, and
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23 Drugscore for each of the 20 medoids along with the RMSD with respect to the X-ray. For the
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25 RMSD calculation, we first aligned the heavy atoms of both backbone and side chains of the
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27 residues constituting the protein binding site, as defined by NanoShaper, between each putative
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29 binding pose and the X-Ray structure of the complex. The RMSD was then calculated on the
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31 heavy atoms of the ligand. In case of RAD51-BRCA2 we used a proper protein-peptide scoring
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33 function, namely HADDOCK score, to rank the 20 medoids³⁹. The fitting has been carried out on
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35 the RAD51 backbone and the RMSD calculation on the BRCA2 backbone, residues from 1523
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37 to 1534, which define the peptide interface contact region (iRMSD). iRMSD, or “interface
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39 RMSD”, which is the RMSD calculated only on the backbone of the residues that are at the
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41 binding interface, is a commonly accepted criterion used for protein-protein docking
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43 evaluation⁴⁰.

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51 The figures of merit used to assess the performance of SMD and other scoring functions in
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53 selecting the near-native binding poses are: i) the coincidence between the best ranked and the
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3 nearest to native medoid (Min to Min); ii) the ability to position the nearest to native medoid
4 within 1 Å (in the case of SMD) or within 2kcal/mol (in the case of scoring functions) of the best
5 ranked pose; and iii) the ability to position the nearest to native medoid within 1 σ (standard
6 deviation) of the best ranked pose. Standard deviation is calculated from the set of RMSDs with
7 respect to initial configuration in the case of SMD and from the set of scores in the remaining
8 cases.
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19 **2.6. Computational molecular dynamics setup.** The algorithm setup and the analyses,
20 excluding the ligand geometric optimization, were performed using BiKi Life Sciences suite 1.3
21 of BiKi Technologies s.r.l. Each compound geometry was optimized via a quantum mechanical
22 approach: electron density calculations were performed at the HF/6-31G* level of theory using
23 the NWChem program⁴¹. Partial charges were derived using the RESP method in
24 Antechamber⁴², while a GAFF⁴³ parameterization was used to achieve the complete topological
25 description of each ligand.
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35 Once the ligand was positioned through the “Residue Placement” tool in BiKi, the system was
36 solvated in an orthorhombic box using TIP3P water model⁴⁴. Adding a suitable number of
37 counter-ions neutralized the overall system. Amber99SB-ildn force field was used⁴⁵. Then, the
38 whole system underwent energy minimization. Four different consecutive equilibration steps
39 were performed: 1) 100 ps in NVT ensemble at 100K with both the protein backbone and ligand
40 restrained (1000 kJ/mol nm²), 2) 100 ps in NVT ensemble at 200K with both the protein
41 backbone and the ligand restrained, 3) 100 ps in NVT ensemble at 300K with the protein free
42 and the ligand restrained, and 4) 1000 ps in NPT ensemble at 300K with the protein free and the
43 ligand restrained. Electrostatics was treated with the cutoff method for short-range interactions
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3 and with the Particle Mesh Ewald method for long-range interactions (rlist = 1.1 nm, cutoff
4 distance = 1.1 nm, VdW distance = 1.1 nm, PME order = 4). The constant temperature
5 conditions were provided using the velocity rescale thermostat⁴⁶, which is a modification of the
6 Berendsen's coupling algorithm⁴⁷. The coordinate output from the last simulation was then used
7 as input to produce the biased molecular dynamics. Finally, 20 replica production runs, 20 ns
8 long in NVT ensemble at 300K, were performed for each complex using C=0.1 (the fraction of
9 the felt force, here 10%), th=0.4 (in nm, representing the switch-off residue distance at which the
10 bias is turned off), a smoothing window size of 1000 samples, and a maximal K(t) of 0.001
11 (maximal steering constant).
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27 3. RESULTS

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30 **3.1. Sampling putative binding poses.** Here, we analyze the method's ability to sample the
31 correct binding pose as a result of a fully flexible and explicitly solvated dynamics that starts
32 from the apo conformation of the target protein, available for 5 out of 8 targets. Results are
33 shown in Table 1. Our figure of merit is the RMSD with respect to the crystal structure of a
34 chosen medoid obtained by clustering the final unbiased part of the binding simulations (see
35 Methods for details). In only two of the analyzed systems the RMSDs of the nearest to native
36 medoid are larger than 2Å, a commonly accepted threshold in docking benchmarks. Also in these
37 cases, namely AChE- Galantamine and GPCR β2- Alprenolol with RMSDs of 2.1Å (crystal
38 resolution 2.4Å) and 2.5Å (3.16Å), respectively, however, the main molecular interactions are
39 reproduced. Remarkably, the simulations sampled configurations very close to the crystal ones in
40 all cases (see Table 1). The same approach was also attempted on a protein-peptide system,
41 namely the RAD51-BRCA2 complex, observing similarly good results. Here, a restraint on the
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local secondary structure of the peptide was applied, to reduce the conformational space to be explored, as detailed in the SI (Table S4).

Table 1. Sampling of binding poses for a diverse set of targets and ligands

#	Target (initial struct.)	Ligand	Holo PDB	Best Medoid RMSD (Å)	Min Obs RMSD (Å)	Crystal Resolution (Å)	RMSD Target initial struct. vs. holo (Å)
1	CDK2 (4EK3)	Staurosporine	4ERW	1.5	1.3	2.0	3.5
		Hymenialdisine	1DM2	1.0	0.5	2.1	4.7
2	CK1D (3UYS)	PF670462	3UZP	0.6	0.3	1.94	1.5
3	AChE (4EY4)	Donepezil	4EY7	2.0	1.4	2.35	1.3
		Galantamine	4EY6	2.1	1.4	2.4	0.9
4	GPCR β 2	ICI 118,551	3NY8	1.0	0.9	2.84	0.9
		Alprenolol	3NYA	2.5	1.6	3.16	0.0
5*	GPCR A2A	T4E	3UZC	1.6	1.2	3.34	0.0
6	SRC (1Y57)	PP1	1QCF	0.9	0.3	2.0	0.7
7*	PNP (1M73)	DADMe Imm-H	1RSZ	1.9	1.0	2.2	3.1
8	RAD51	BRCA2	1N0W	1.9	0.9	1.7	0.0

* for these targets 3 entrances to the site were identified and 3 campaigns were performed

Column 4: PDB code of the holo structure of the target. Column 5: the RMSD wrt. crystal of the nearest to crystal medoid obtained by clustering (see the Methods). Column 6: minimum RMSD observed throughout the simulation. Column 7: resolution of the crystal of the complex. Column 8: RMSD between the initial conformation of the binding site and that of the complex.

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3 Although dynamic docking is different in many respects from classic molecular docking,
4 conventional docking simulations were performed on targets #1 to #7 using Autodock Vina⁴⁸ and
5 rDock⁴⁹. In Autodock Vina all the attracting residues and the dihedral angles of the ligand have
6 been left flexible while in rDock only terminal OH and NH3 groups on the protein in vicinity of
7 the binding site were allowed to be fully flexible. Further details can be found in Tables S5 and
8 S6 and are briefly summarized here in Figure 1. With these settings, no pose with $\text{RMSD} < 2\text{\AA}$
9 was identified by Autodock Vina among the first 20 ones, while at least one pose with $\text{RMSD} <$
10 2\AA was observed with rDock for 6 out of 10 complexes (see Figure 1a). Then, we considered
11 separately the performance of rDock on the systems where the RMSD between the input
12 conformation of the target and that of the holo complex, reported in column 8 of Table 1, is
13 larger or smaller than 1\AA . The results reported in Figure 1b, rDock1 and rDock2 series, show a
14 remarkable sensitivity to this aspect, in contrast to what occurs with MD-Binding. Finally, we
15 also tested the sensitivity of the performance of rDock with respect to the input conformation of
16 the ligand, by feeding the program with the same ligand structures obtained after the
17 minimization and equilibration steps, which precede the execution of MD-Binding. Results,
18 reported in Figure 1b, (rDock3 series) show a marginal deterioration of the performance. To
19 highlight the importance for molecular docking tools of the complementarity between the
20 conformations of the target and the ligand and of the amplitude of the conformational space that
21 needs to be explored, we performed a rigid self-docking with Autodock Vina on target #5, where
22 we have only the holo conformation, obtaining very good results (see Table S8). Overall, these
23 results are in agreement with what it is known about the performance of molecular docking when
24 non-cognate structures are used^{7, 50}.

As a further test, we performed two Steered MD campaigns of 20 replicas each, using the distance between the centers of mass of the ligand and the same residues composing the S set in the MD-binding method. This was done for the CDK2-STU and the CDK2-HYM complexes. In no replica the final RMSD wrt. crystal goes below 4.5Å. Related details concerning the methods and results are in the Supplementary Information (see Table S9).

Figure 1. Performance of Molecular Docking tools. a) Statistics of RMSD wrt. crystal of the

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3 first 20 poses provided by Autodock Vina (in blue) and rDock (in red) when they are inputted
4 with crystal ligand structures. **b)** Performance of rDock on the complexes presenting a RMSD
5 in protein binding site between inputted and crystal structure larger than 1 Å (rDock1 series),
6 and lower than 1 Å (rDock2 series). rDock3 series shows the performance of rDock when the
7 inputted ligand structures are subjected to energy minimization and equilibration (the same
8 preprocessing done in the MD Binding procedure).
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20 **3.2. Identification of near-native binding poses.** Here, we analyze the method's ability to
21 identify near-native binding poses from among the configurations explored during the simulation
22 campaign. This ability is essential for the global viability of a dynamical docking approach. It is
23 achieved by first exploiting the adaptivity of the bias. As detailed in the Methods, by
24 construction, the bias gradually switches off as the algorithm judges that the ligand is
25 approaching the bound state, so that the last part of the simulation becomes unbiased. In some
26 runs, this condition is never met and they are therefore immediately discarded (see, for example,
27 Figure S1). Then, the last unbiased pieces of the remaining trajectories are collected and
28 clustered via a k-medoid approach, imposing 20 final clusters. Finally, the corresponding
29 medoids are ranked based on their stability, assessed via RMSD deviation, during a short run of
30 unrestrained scaled MD (SMD)³⁷ (see the Methods). As shown in Figure 2, this approach
31 provided equal or better performance relative to scoring functions traditionally adopted in
32 molecular docking, namely Autodock4⁵¹, Vina⁴⁸ and DSX DrugScore⁵². In this respect, the most
33 relevant result is the ability of SMD to map the best rank to the best pose, which makes the
34 overall approach particularly efficient. Interestingly, the different ranking approaches were
35 challenged to recognize a very bad conformation: a head-to-tail inversion in the case of the drug
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donepezil binding to the enzyme acetylcholinesterase. Unlike the tested scoring functions, which could not reject it so clearly, SMD identified this unlikely binding pose and ranked it among the lowest positions. (see Supplementary Information for complete data). Another interesting outcome is that the main interactions between the binding partners were recapitulated. Moreover, the simulated pose correctly reports the water-mediated interaction that can be observed in the crystal structure of one of the examined cases, namely the in the CK1D case (see Figure S2).

Interestingly, the discriminating ability of SMD seems to extend somehow also to peptide ligands.

Figure 2. Ranking of putative bound poses. Performance of SMD and widely adopted docking scoring functions in selecting the near-native binding poses. Three figures of merit were used: the ability to map the best rank to the best configuration (Min to Min), the ability to position the best configuration within 1 Å or 2kcal/mol of the best ranked pose, and the ability to position the actual best configuration within 1 σ (standard deviation) of the best ranked pose. Target #8 was not included in this comparison, since the considered scoring functions have been tuned for small chemical compounds rather than for peptides.

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3 To assess this aspect, we compared the results it provided on the RAD51-BRCA2 complex
4 with those of a scoring function specifically designed for the protein-protein binding, namely that
5 of HADDOCK⁵³. As shown in Table S3, the difference of SMD-based score, that is the iRMSD
6 averaged over 5 ns of SMD, between the nearest to native pose and the best scored one was of
7 0.7 Å, corresponding to 0.16 σ (standard deviation of the SMD-scores of that campaign). The
8 HADDOCK score difference between nearest native and best scoring pose was instead of
9 slightly more than one standard deviation.
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21 **3.3. Similarity to near-native binding paths.** To the best of our knowledge, no experimental
22 study to date has provided a full atomistic characterization of an entire binding process.
23 However, in principle, long plain-MD approaches can model a realistic binding process,
24 provided that sufficient computational resources are available. Ligand-binding to three of our
25 targets (namely #4, #6 and #7) has already been studied via plain MD, and these simulated
26 binding events are the best available comparison reference for our biased trajectories. We
27 therefore focus on the formation of three complexes, namely β_2 adrenergic receptor and
28 alprenolol, SRC kinase and PP1 inhibitor, and purine nucleoside phosphorylase and DADMe-
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44 **3.4. β_2 -adrenergic binding alprenolol.** The G-protein-coupled receptor β_2 -adrenergic (β_2 -AR)
45 is an important target for hypertension and several heart diseases. DE Shaw and co-workers have
46 used extensive plain MD to study how this receptor interacts and binds with the inverse agonist
47 alprenolol¹⁰. We analyzed our best binding route with two binding trajectories obtained via plain
48 MD and kindly provided by DE Shaw Research. The comparison showed interesting shared
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3 features. The recognition is very similar to that described in Dror et al., involving the same
4 contacts in the same temporal order. As shown in Figure 3, although the alprenolol molecule
5 reached the entrance from different positions and with different orientations, the binding paths
6 followed the same two-steps molecular mechanism. First, alprenolol reorients so that its
7 hydrophobic group binds to the extracellular vestibule surface (Figure 3, upper row). Then, it
8 penetrates into the binding pocket through the gate closing-opening mechanism between Tyr308
9 and Phe193 to form the salt bridges between the ammonium moiety and the carboxylate of
10 Asp113 (Figure 3, lower row).
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24 **3.5. PP1 binding SRC kinase.** Another complex that was previously studied by extensive
25 plain MD is PP1 inhibiting SRC kinase, a relevant biological target for cancer therapy. The PP1
26 binding mode is characterized by a well-defined hydrogen bond network between the receptor,
27 the ligand, and the surrounding water molecules. These interactions are only reproduced in one
28 out of 20 medoids, which the SMD-based approach correctly identified. Characterization of the
29 SRC-PP1 binding path was done by means of two different campaigns (20 runs each) with the
30 ligand starting in different positions. The two binding paths leading to near-native binding, one
31 per campaign, were compared with each other and with one long plain-MD trajectory kindly
32 provided by DE Shaw Research¹⁵.
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Figure 3. Binding of alprenolol to the β 2-adrenergic receptor. Time sequence of the alprenolol binding process studied by MD-Binding (ligand in red and relevant side chains in orange) and plain MD¹⁰ (ligand in blue and relevant side chains in ice blue). Simulated times are reported in red for MD-Binding and in blue for plain MD. In both simulations alprenolol approaches the extracellular vestibule with the hydrophobic ring first and then it rotates to form the salt bridges (upper row). Moreover, in both simulations, Tyr308 and Phe193 separate and let the ligand's hydrophobic group pass through them. After the binding occurs, the gate closes (lower row).

Interestingly, despite the different starting positions and the much larger sterically available space, in all cases the PP1 ligand accessed the site passing near a relatively small hydrophobic patch, as summarized in Figure 4. In the accelerated simulation, after spending a few ns in this region, the ligand enters the binding site with the heteroaromatic moiety, i.e. pyrazole and pyrimidinylamine. Only later does the ligand rearrange, positioning the toluene ring at the bottom of the binding site, recapitulating the main interactions between the heteroaromatic ring and the Met341 and Glu339 residues.

3.6. DADMe binding purine nucleoside phosphorylase. We compared the successful binding trajectory obtained with our dedicated bias to the set of binding trajectories obtained

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3 **Figure 4. Binding of PP1 to SRC kinase.** Binding paths observed in our biased runs (in orange
4 and red) and in the plain MD described in Shan et al. (in blue)¹⁵. Despite initial starting positions
5 and orientations are different, and that the sterically accessible region (in cyan) is quite large, all
6 ligands go through the same narrower region (indicated by the convergence of the three
7 differently colored clouds representing the three ligands' paths). Subsequent analysis showed
8 that the preferred paths pass near the only hydrophobic patch found in the site entrance.
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20 4. DISCUSSION and CONCLUSIONS

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22 The method presented here addresses the main hurdles faced by the computer simulation of
23 protein-ligand binding processes. Protein-ligand binding poses can sometimes be reproduced
24 with a high level of accuracy by plain-MD simulations in the microsecond-to-millisecond
25 timescale, or by shorter, but more numerous, simulations. However, these approaches require a
26 great deal of time and resources, which is rarely compatible with routine drug discovery projects,
27 where, ideally, many compounds would be computationally investigated prior to medicinal
28 chemistry experiments⁴. The results presented herein indicate that a partially guided approach
29 can provide insightful information in an aggregate time which is, on average, 2-3 orders of
30 magnitude shorter than that required by plain MD even in cases where a non-cognate site
31 conformation is chosen to start the simulation, therefore requiring a substantial rearrangement of
32 binding site residues. Moreover, this approach carries the additional advantage of being divisible
33 into trivially parallel short simulations.
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50 To attain its aim, the method exploits electrostatic attraction to induce recognition and binding.
51 Rather than localizing the attraction on centers of mass, as often reported in the literature, it
52 spreads it over a large number of atoms, facilitating concerted movements. Moreover, it favors
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3 the exploration of low-energy, physically sound paths via a suitably adaptive behavior. At the
4 end of the simulations, near-native binding poses were identified by clustering and SMD-based
5 conformation ranking procedures. Choosing the attracting residues on the protein side is a critical
6 part of the method and examples of the deterioration of the performance induced by a wrong
7 choice are reported in the SI. Our criterion here consists in a down-selection, chiefly based on
8 geometric criteria, of the residues composing the binding site. Remarkably, the same choice of
9 residues provided equally good results in type-1 inhibitors of three different kinases, namely
10 CDK2, CK1D, and SRC kinase. A useful feature of the method is the possibility to include a
11 priori knowledge about the binding with no difficulty, as it was done in the β 2-adrenergic case,
12 where the interaction of ligands with Asp113 is widely accepted. In the performed validation
13 tests, we targeted the known orthosteric binding sites. However, the approach is expected to
14 work also in case of targeting allosteric or cryptic sites.
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31 Interestingly, the availability of the holo conformation of the protein, which lacks in the most
32 challenging, and also interesting, cases, does not seem to be an essential requisite to achieve a
33 good performance of the MD-Binding method. This is one of the main differences with
34 conventional molecular docking, where the differences between self- and cross-docking results
35 may be striking.
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42 To challenge the extent of applicability of the method, we applied it to a relevant protein-
43 peptide case, obtaining very promising results, although further studies and some adaptation are
44 required to assess whether the novel methodology is fully suitable for protein-peptide and, in the
45 long term, protein-protein systems.
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51 A promising feature of our approach might be the ability to identify prominent mechanistic
52 features of the binding process. There is increasing interest in the scientific community in
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3 understanding the path that characterizes the binding and thus identifying the relevant
4 intermediates that could explain non-obvious kinetic behaviors, such as traps and allosteric sites,
5 as a new dimension to be exploited in drug design. In this respect, the binding trajectories
6 generated by our method were compared to the available reference paths (generated via plain
7 MD) and showed interesting mechanistic commonalities.

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10 A further aspect to consider is that a reasonable initial guess binding path can be exploited to
11 feed traditional path-based enhanced sampling techniques to obtain free-energy profile estimates
12 along binding and, finally, chemical affinity^{54, 55}. Interested readers can apply the techniques
13 described in this paper by obtaining a trial version of the BiKi LifeSciences software suite by
14 requesting it on the site <http://www.bikitech.com>.

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17 The present methodology seeks to fulfill two divergent requirements. These are a) accuracy,
18 which can, in principle, be obtained by extensive MD simulations, and b) speed, which is
19 particularly necessary when many compounds must be investigated to drive a lead discovery
20 campaign. Here, using electrostatics as the bias to accelerate MD simulations, we obtained
21 accurate binding poses and routes much faster than via plain MD. The obtained results
22 corroborate our initial hypothesis that electrostatics is suitable for building a good attractive
23 basin even for binding processes that naturally are not driven by electrostatics. The presented
24 approach paves the way for a feasible and efficient dynamic docking simulation, which delivers
25 the “full movie” rather than just the “final scene”. Dynamic docking is a quite different concept
26 from conventional molecular docking,⁵⁶ providing a wider wealth of information at a larger
27 computational cost. It can also be used as a second line alternative, in cases where the dynamic
28 phenomena accompanying binding prevent static docking from predicting the correct
29 conformation of the complex. We believe this will remarkably broaden the scope and the impact

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3 of MD in every discipline concerning protein-ligand interaction and opens up new avenues for
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5 developing innovative drug discovery methods.
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18 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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21 The Authors are shares owners of BiKi Technologies s.r.l., a company that commercializes
22
23 software solutions for medicinal chemistry including the presented method.
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39 ASSOCIATED CONTENT

41 **Supporting Information.**

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47 Supplementary results with accompanied figures and tables referred to in the main text (.pdf).
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49 Supplementary Movies (in .avi format) showing the simulated binding of Alprenolol to the β 2
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51 Adrenergic GPCR, PP1 inhibitor to Src kinase and DADMe Imm-H to Purine Nucleoside
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3 Phosphorylase. The corresponding structures (.gro) and trajectories (.xtc) format are also
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5 provided.
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8 This information is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.
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